

Horizon 2020 ULTRAWAVE

Ultra capacity wireless layer beyond 100 GHz based on millimetre wave Traveling Wave Tubes

WP7. Deliverable D7.6: Communication & Dissemination Report

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Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is a summary of the Dissemination and Communication activities carried out in the framework of the H2020 ULTRAWAVE project during the reporting period comprised between September 2017 and February 2019. These actions have been coordinated through WP7 which is aimed promoting and disseminating the project vision and technical developments to the greatest number of actors who would be potentially interested. It comprises the scientific community, the industrial ecosystem, policy makers, standardization bodies, potential end-users as well as the general public.

This document is structured as follows. Section 1 provides an overview of the general aim of Dissemination and Communication activities in the framework of ULTRAWAVE. A summary of the dissemination activities, including the project corporate identity, website, newsletters, scientific publication in journals and conferences, participation in international conferences and workshops advisory board and collaboration with other projects of the same call, is given in Section 2. The communication activities carried out are presented in Section 3. In particular, the press releases launched, the promotional material elaborated and the social media channels used are reported in this section. Finally, Section 4 provides some figures to evaluate the dissemination and communication progress.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dissemination and communication activities are recognised as key elements within ULTRAWAVE. A special effort has been made during the first year of the project to promote the project vision and technology and to ensure that these activities are properly addressed and managed.

The main goal of dissemination and communication activities is to reach out to the widest possible range of stakeholders to promote further exploitation of the project results. These tasks aim at ensuring that the results gained during the course of the project exert their full impact in a coordinated and resource-efficient way, and in synergy with the activities of the different Work Packages.

Different dissemination activities have been planned and executed, having been tailored to match the interest of different target audiences.

This report, Deliverable 7.6, lists the activities carried out during the period between September 2017 and February 2019. These activities include framework activities for the whole project, such as the establishment of a corporate project identity and social network channels; the elaboration of a Data Management Plan; as well as specific communication and dissemination activities, including scientific, industrial and general publications, press releases, meetings, etc; and, finally also the joint activities with other projects of the same call.

2. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

1. Project identity

The aim of the established of a project identity is important to ease the authentication of the project materials and to strengthen the dissemination and communication of ULTRAWAVE vision and technology. Our project identity ensures that all communication and dissemination products, including reports, the website, flyers, posters, presentation slides and other promotional materials have a uniform look. It also greatly facilitates recognition by stakeholders.

With this aim a logo, Figure 1, was developed at the beginning of the project.

Figure 1. ULTRAWAVE logo

Additionally, a common template for presentations has also been developed, as shown in Figure 2.

ULTRAWAVE template

Figure 2. ULTRAWAVE Powerpoint template

All dissemination materials include the EU emblem and the accompanying text of: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 762119”*.

ULTRAWAVE partners are required to use the logos, templates and other visual identity material developed in the framework of WP7 for all their dissemination activities related to the project.

2. Website

ULTRAWAVE public website is aimed at providing a vision of the project to the general public as well as detailed information for groups such as the European industry, scientific community, and potential end-users such as telecommunication operators. The public website is therefore the core element of the external communication strategy of ULTRAWAVE to raise awareness about the project activities, facilitate the diffusion of the project's results and promote the exploitation of the results. This will be the main communication channel to be utilized in ULTRAWAVE. Figure 3 shows a screenshot of the website home page.

Figure 3. ULTRAWAVE homepage

The project URL, www.ultrawave2020.eu, has been active since July 19th 2017. Originally, the website included basic information about the project and the kick-off meeting. In September 2017 (M1) all sections of the website were active. Since its launch, the website is being regularly updated to maintain a sustained interest in the project activities. Updates highlight project-related news, presence of ULTRAWAVE in the press, events, publications, newsletter issues, and other activities dedicated to dissemination.

The website has been structured in seven sections to present different aspects of ULTRAWAVE activities: About, Technology, Results, Links, News&Events, Media and Contact. The first section provides a summary of ULTRAWAVE goals and context, a description of the project consortium and a short overview of the work plan. A pdf brochure summarizing this information can also be downloaded. The composition of the User Group is also described. Information about the core technologies to be pushed forward by the project, in a language aimed at non-technical audiences, is presented in the Technology section. It also provides the main technological challenges to be faced by the consortium. In Results, an up-to-date list of the publications, deliverables, including the downloadable pdf files of public deliverables and also the project newsletters is provided. A list of news with information such as meetings, presentations, etc is also available from the web to keep the project community updated. Links to other research projects focusing on related topics are also provided with special emphasis on the other projects of the call H2020 ICT-9-2017, which jointly with ULTRAWAVE have created the “ICT Beyond 5G” Cluster. It is a joint dissemination initiative to leverage the seven consortium resources.

The website also has links to the ULTRAWAVE Twitter account as well as the LinkedIn one. It also contains a YouTube uploaded short video summarizing ULTRAWAVE goals.

The audience of the website has been followed using the tool Google Analytics with the objective of monitoring web statistics to assess the website visibility, identify its most popular webpages, and optimize its design for improved user experience (Figure 4).

In the period under evaluation more than 5000 pages associated to ULTRAWAVE have been visualized by more than 1000 users.

Figure 4. Audience report on project website¹.

The geographical origin of the users is summarized in Figure 5. It can be seen that the country where more users are located is Unites States, with a 22%. It is followed by China (13%) and United Kingdom (10%).

Figure 5. Geographical origin of users.

¹ Users: Number of users that have had at least one session within the selected date range. Includes both new and returning users.

Sessions: Total number of sessions within the date range. A session is the period time a user is actively engaged with the website.

Pageviews: Total number of pages viewed (5068 pages).

Pages/Session (Average Page Depth) is the average number of pages viewed during a session (2.51).

The average length of a Session.

The public deliverable D7.2 associated with the launch of project website was delivered on November 2017 as scheduled and it is available in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/record/1243019#.W5pSYvZ9jIU>). The Milestone 7.1 related to the website was consequently also completed in November 2017.

3. Newsletters

A series of newsletters has been started for communication and dissemination of the project progress with stakeholders and the ULTRAWAVE community. The newsletters are in English.

The first newsletter was published in March 2018 and the second one in January 2019.

The typical content includes technical updates, report on dissemination activities, past and planned and a section “Meet a partner”. In this section, each issue will host the profile of one ULTRAWAVE partner.

These newsletters are posted on the website, announced on Twitter, and sent by email to a selection of industrial and academic contacts. Both issues are included in Annex I.

4. Publications in journals and conferences

During this period, the main aim of the scientific publications has been the introduction of the ULTRAWAVE general concept, technical approach, and research activities to potential users, industry and expert groups.

A journal paper on some initial design aspects of the G-band TWT was published:

- R. Basu, L.R. Billa, R. Letizia, C. Paoloni “Design of sub-THz traveling wave tubes for high data rate long range wireless links”, *Semicond. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 33, pp 124009, 30th October 2018.

Some conference papers were published:

- B. Vidal, “Beyond 5G wireless backhaul enhanced by photonic technology”, XV International Scientific and Technical Conference, “Optical Technologies for Telecommunications”. Ufa (Russia), 20-22 November 2018.
- C. Paoloni, “Ultra Capacity Wireless Layer Beyond 100 GHz Based on Millimeter Wave Traveling Wave Tubes”, European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC), Lubiana (Slovenia), 18-21 June 2018.
- B. Vidal, “Photonic-assisted G-band wireless links for 5G backhaul”, 20th International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON), Bucharest (Romania), 1-5 July 2018.
- G. Ulisse, V. Krozer, “Folded waveguide traveling wave tube in a parallel configuration with a single electron beam”, IEEE International Vacuum Electronics Conference (IVEC), Monterey (USA), 24-26 April 2018.

Figure 6. Claudio Paoloni presenting at the EuCNC (Slovenia, June 2018)

Figure 7. B. Vidal presenting at ICTON (Romania, July 2018)

- C. Paoloni, R. Letizia, V. Krozer, M. Marilier, S. Boppel, A. Ramirez, B. Vidal, E. Limiti, R. Zimmerman, “Toward 100 Gbps Wireless Networks Enabled by Millimeter Wave Traveling Wave Tubes”, IEEE International Vacuum Electronics Conference (IVEC), Monterey (USA) 24-26 April 2018.
- C. Paoloni, “Point to Multipoint at Millimetre Waves Above 90 GHz”, 26th European Conference on Networks and Communications (EUCNC 2017), Oulu (Finland), 12-15 June 2017.

Several invited talks have been given to disseminate the project goals:

- C. Paoloni, “Novel High Capacity Millimetre Wave Wireless Networks Enabled by Traveling Wave Tubes”, CST European User Conference (EUC), Unterschleissheim, Germany, 4th June 2018. Plenary talk.
- C. Paoloni, “Millimeter wave wireless communications toward 300 GHz”, University of California Davis, US, 5th December 2017.
- C. Paoloni, “Traveling Wave Tubes for Millimeter Wave Wireless Communications Toward 300 GHz”, SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory, Stanford, US, 4th December 2017.
- C. Paoloni, “Millimetre Wave Point to Multipoint Enabled by a Novel W-band Traveling Wave Tube”, ARMMS Conference, St Noet, UK, 13-14 November 2017.
- C. Paoloni, “Wireless Communications Towards the 300 GHz”, WM-06 THz Electronics Technology for Communications and Sensing, EUMW 2017, Nuremberg, Germany, 9th October 2017.
- C. Paoloni, “THz vacuum electronics”, Teranet Terahertz Roadmap Conference, Southampton, UK, 11th July 2017.

Figure 8. Claudio Paoloni presenting at the EUC (Germany, June 2018)

Moreover, ULTRAWAVE has also been promoted through talks at workshops and seminars:

- A. Ramírez, “Ampliando las fronteras de la alta capacidad inalámbrica”, XXII Meeting of the ESNOG (Spanish Network Operators Group), Valencia, October 25th, 2018.
- C. Paoloni, “Wireless communication networks toward 300 GHz”, IET Colloquium on Millimetre-wave and Terahertz Engineering & Technology 2018, Birmingham, UK, 1st March 2018. This talk was given by R. Basu on behalf of C. Paoloni.

Figure 9. Rupa Basu (Lancaster Univ., left) and Andy Sutton (British operator BT, right) at the Cambridge Wireless event on Radio Technology for 5G (UK, March 2018)

- C. Paoloni, “Ultracapacity layer enabled by novel traveling wave tubes“, Towards TeraHertz Communications Workshop, Brussels, Belgium, 7th March 2018.
- E. Pinilla, Cicle de Conferències, “Universitat de València”, Valencia , Spain, 26th October 2017.
- J.R. Ruiz, UN Technology Fair, Valencia, Spain, 23-24 October 2017.

Figure 10. C. Paoloni presenting at the first “Towards THz Communications Workshop”(Belgium, March 2018)

Finally, an industrial article has been published in the period:

- C. Paoloni, “Novel high capacity millimeter wave wireless networks enabled by traveling wave tubes”, SIMULIA Community News, edited Dassault Systèmes, May 2018

Although dissemination has been intense during this period, relatively few journal papers have been published so far since the partners have been developing procedures and preliminary tests to the newly developed components. It is expected that as the work progresses, the number of papers will raise.

5. Participation in conference and event

Members of ULTRAWAVE participated to:

- IET Colloquium on Millimetre-wave and Terahertz Engineering & Technology 2018, Birmingham, UK, 1st March 2018
- European Microwave Week 2017, Nuremberg, Germany, 9th October 2017
- European Microwave Week 2018, Madrid, Spain, 25-27 September 2018
- ARMMS Conference, St Noet, UK, 13-14 November 2017
- CST European User Conference (EUC), Unterschleissheim, Germany, 4th June 2018.
- 26th European Conference on Networks and Communications (EUCNC 2017), Oulu, Finland, 12-15 June 2017.
- IEEE International Vacuum Electronics Conference (IVEC), Monterey, USA, 24-26 April 2018.
- European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC), Lubliana, Slovenia, 18-21 June 2018.
- Teranet Terahertz Roadmap Conference, Southampton, UK, 11th July 2017.
- UN Technology Fair, Valencia, Spain, 23-24 October 2017
- Workshop IET 5G - The Advent, London, UK, 30 January 2019.

6. Conference and event organisation

- “Second Terahertz Communication” workshop, 7th March 2019, Brussels, Belgium, General Chair Claudio Paoloni.
- “Second Workshop on Economics and Adoption of Millimeter Wave Technology in Future Networks” 2019, WCNC 2019 Marrakech, Morocco, Chair Claudio Paoloni.
- “From Evolution to Revolution, a roadmap for beyond 5G” workshop, 5G World Forum, 2019, 30th September – 2nd October, Dresden, Germany, General Chair Claudio Paoloni.

Details on the progress of the workshops to be held will be given in the D7.10 deliverable.

7. Award

ULTRAWAVE was shortlisted in the ‘Collaborate to Innovate’ Awards 2018 from the UK magazine “The Engineer” in the category “Information, Data & Connectivity” (Figure 11).

Figure 11. “Collaborate to Innovate” Award by UK magazine “The Engineer”.

The press release from the University of Lancaster can be seen in Figure 12.

National award shortlisting for beyond 5G high-speed wireless network research

10 August 2018 15:47

ULTRAWAVE consortium researchers

A major Lancaster University-led international research project that will deliver unprecedented high-speed wireless data coverage has been shortlisted for a national award.

The **ULTRAWAVE** programme is a European Union Horizon 2020 funded project that is developing cutting edge technologies to make ubiquitous wireless data speed of up to 100 gigabits per second possible by exploiting the millimetre wave spectrum up to 300 GHz.

The programme has been shortlisted in the 'Information, Data and Connectivity' category in 2018 The Engineer magazine's **Collaborate to Innovate** awards.

The ULTRAWAVE concept is to create an ultra-capacity wireless transmission layer that is flexible and easy to deploy. This layer would feed data to a mesh of hundreds of small cells, for providing high speed internet to smartphones and tablets in high density city areas, solving the huge increase of data demand.

The ULTRAWAVE system will provide, for the first time, wide area coverage at millimetre waves by using significant transmission power that can only be generated through novel millimetre travelling wave tubes. The ultra-high data rate wireless layer will be enabled through the convergence of three technologies – vacuum electronics, solid-state electronics and photonics.

Professor Claudio Paoloni, project coordinator of ULTRAWAVE and Head of **Engineering** at Lancaster University, said: "I am delighted that ULTRAWAVE has been shortlisted for this prestigious award. It rewards the high standing and collaborative effort of the eight international project partners to overcome the actual technology barriers for providing ubiquitous and unprecedented high speed internet to our smartphones."

The award winners will be announced at a ceremony in London on November 6.

“
 I am delighted that ULTRAWAVE has been shortlisted for this prestigious award. It rewards the high standing and collaborative effort of the eight international project partners to overcome the actual technology barriers for providing ubiquitous and unprecedented high speed internet to our smartphones.”

Professor Claudio Paoloni

Share this story

Figure 12. Press release by the University of Lancaster about the nomination of ULTRAWAVE in the category “Information, Data & Connectivity” of the “Collaborate to Innovate” award by the UK magazine “The Engineer”.

8. Advisory board

ULTRAWAVE has established an “Advisory Board” to keep its activities in the track of real market needs. Experts from relevant companies in the field of wireless communications have been invited to follow the progress of ULTRAWAVE research programme and technological results. The Advisory Board will contribute to enhance the visibility of the project-developed technology. Additionally, this board will also provide valuable feedback and advice on the project activities to maximize the success of ULTRAWAVE technology.

The composition of the Advisory Board is:

- Valerio Frascolla, from Intel (Germany).
- Renato Lombardi, from Huawei (Italy)
- Mauro Boldi, from Telecom Italia (Italy).

- Chris Buck, from Filtronic (UK).
- Emilio Calvanese, from CEA LETI (France).

9. ICT Beyond 5G Cluster activities

ULTRAWAVE and the other H2020 five projects, TERRANOVA, TERAPOD, EPIC, DREAM and WORTECS, funded through the H2020 call ICT-09-2017 “Networking beyond 5G” and recently Thor funded by a call EU/Japan have joined forces to collaborate in the dissemination of their activities with the aim leveraging resources, gain momentum and achieve stronger impact. The projects are members of the ICT Beyond 5G Cluster.

In this framework, the first joint activity was sharing a booth at the exhibition of the European Microwave Week (EuMW) which was held at Madrid from the 25th to the 27th September 2018. EuMW is the largest conference event on microwaves in Europe. The experience was very successful with good interest from delegates and companies present the EuMW exhibition. The combination of the dissemination activities strongly reinforced the visibility of the projects.

This positive experience highlighted the importance of these joint activities and since then regular teleconferences have been scheduled to discuss and plan key events to target.

The cluster is organizing the second edition of the “Towards THz communications” workshop, following the successful first workshop held in 2018. The workshop will be held in Brussels (Belgium) on the 7th of March 2019. The steering committee of the ICT Beyond 5G cluster managed the organisation. Claudio Paoloni, ULTRAWAVE coordinator, is one of the General Chairs. The workshop agenda consists of one plenary and three technical sessions. The plenary session includes three plenary talks from international top researchers from USA and Japan. Six invited speakers will be given in the three sessions following the plenary session.

The cluster will be present at the exhibition of the EUCNC (European Conference on Networks and Communications) to be held in Valencia (Spain) in June 2019 with a booth.

Claudio Paoloni is also General Chair of the workshop at 5G World Summit, 30 September-2 October 2019, Dresden, Germany, organised by the cluster.

In parallel to these clustering activities, ULTRAWAVE partners are eager to continue interactions and collaboration with other European research projects in order to leverage the technical results and amplify their impact and will intent to increase contacts with operators, service providers and standardization bodies, with greater emphasis on exploitation.

Figure 13. Claudio Paoloni discussing with Edward Wasige (University Glasgow) during the EuMW 2018 (Spain, September 2018)

Figure 14. Common “ICT B5G cluster” booth at EuMW Exhibition 2018 (Spain, September 2018)

3. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

In addition to the previously reported activities which focused on the dissemination of the project results, ULTRAWAVE is also carrying out communication activities for promoting the project and its findings and for maximizing the social impact of the project results.

This section presents the communication activities undertaken to promote the objectives and results of ULTRAWAVE in different mass media and social media channels to reach a wide audience, composed of both experts and non-experts.

1. Press releases

Several press releases in English, Spanish and German were launched at the beginning of the project. A first press release announcing the start of ULTRAWAVE was produced by the University of Lancaster. Additionally, the UPV also distributed a press release among several Spanish media. Most partners included news related to the project on their respective websites.

These press releases distributed to general press magazines and other media, reached very wide audiences. Among others, the British magazine “The Engineer” (Figure 4), the website www.sciencedaily.com and the Spanish general newspaper “La Vanguardia” (Figure 5) informed about the start and goals of ULTRAWAVE project.

Figure 15. Article published in the professional British magazine “The Engineer” (19/9/2017)

Figure 16. Article published in the general Spanish newspaper “La Vanguardia” (12/09/2017)

The public deliverable D7.1 associated with the launch of the Press Release was delivered on September 2017 as scheduled and it is available in Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/record/1243016#.W5pRR_Z9jiU).

2. Promotional materials

Promotional materials have been developed to raise awareness on the project activities through different events. A first brochure containing general information about the project, its objectives and the composition of the consortium was produced. It is available for download from ULTRAWAVE website and has also been printed.

Additionally, a second brochure, especially targeted for exhibitions and conferences has been designed and printed. These have been distributed, for the moment, in EuCNC (Ljubjana, Slovenia, 18-21 June 2018), ICTON (Bucharest, Romania, 1-5 July 2018) and EuMW (Madrid, Spain, 23-28 September 2018). The brochures are shown in Annex II.

3. Social networks

The consortium has identified several social media channels to promote the project and reach the widest public: Twitter, LinkedIn and ResearchGate.

A Twitter account has been created (@ultrawave2020) to reach wider audiences. During the first year, 70 Tweets have been posted. They include information about the project, participation by consortium members in conferences and seminars as well as news and information about project meetings. The account has so far 58 followers.

A number of tweets are also generated by the Twitter account of the coordinator @CIPaoloni with more than 10000 contacts.

A project site has also been created in professional social media platforms to enhance the visibility of the project results among professional audiences. A group has been set up in the professional platform LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8628007/>). It is a very valuable platform to reach a large number of ICT professionals. The group is made of 16 members, all linked to the project, with thousands of contacts in academia and industry.

Posts are distributed by the LinkedIn account of the coordinator.

In addition, a project has been created in the scientific site ResearchGate (<https://www.researchgate.net/project/Ultrawave-2>). The profiles in both platforms include links to direct interested viewers to the project website.

Both Twitter and LinkedIn pages are linked from the project website.

4. Video and YouTube ULTRAWAVE Channel

A promotional video has been released by the ULTRAWAVE YouTube channel, LinkedIn and Twitter. It has also been linked through the project website.

The video is a teaser for the main aspects of the project in a simple and intuitive way (Figure 6). So far it has been viewed 164 times.

Figure 17. Snapshot of ULTRAWAVE Twitter

Top Tweet earned 946 impressions

The New @EU_H2020 ULTRAWAVE to bring #wireless outdoor #networks up to 300 GHz starts today. Follow us ultrawave2020.eu @LancsUniEng pic.twitter.com/HRXCkM4V1o

2 retweets 2 likes

Figure 18. Top tweet from ULTRAWAVE Twitter account

Figure 19. Snapshots from ULTRAWAVE promotional video

Figure 20. ULTRAWAVE YouTube Channel

4. EVALUATION OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Dissemination and communication activities are key tools to maximise the impact of the project throughout the lifetime of ULTRAWAVE and beyond. For this reason, the planned dissemination activities of ULTRAWAVE have been properly tailored to different audiences to ensure that the different stakeholders are aware of the benefits and advantages provided by the new ULTRAWAVE technology.

To achieve a successful dissemination and communication strategy it is important to monitor and assess these actions in order to know if the foreseen activities are reaching the expected goals. Thus, dissemination and communication activities are being regularly assessed both qualitatively and quantitatively and closely monitored using participation statistics, search metrics and other established indicators of media use.

Table 1 and Table 2 summarize the dissemination and communication activities reported during this period.

Type of dissemination activities	Number
Website	1
Participation in conferences: EUCNC 2017 (1 talk), IVEC 2018 (2), ICTON 2018 (1), EuCNC 2018 (1), OTT18 (1)	6
Participation in workshops: EUMW 2017, Teranet Terahertz Roadmap Conference 2017, ARMMS Conference 2017, EU Towards TeraHertz Communications Workshop 2018, IET Colloquium on Millimetre-wave and Terahertz Engineering & Technology 2018, EUC18	6
Newsletter (Issues #1, #2)	2
Collaboration with other EU projects – ICT Beyond 5G Cluster	6

Table 1. Reported dissemination activities.

Type of communication activities	Number
Press release (English, Spanish and German)	3
Social Media (Twitter, LinkedIn, ResearchGate)	3
Multimedia: YouTube video	1
Non-scientific (non-peer reviewed) articles: SIMULIA Community News	1

Table 2. Reported communication activities.

5. CONCLUSION

The deliverable D 7.6 provides a summary of the dissemination and communication activities carried out by the consortium partners with the aim to promote ongoing activities and results. The reported activities show a substantial dissemination effort, resulting in considerable high number of contacts among the targeted audience and a wide visibility of the project both at local and international levels.

The project website is the main medium in the dissemination strategy since it provides the adequate platform to gather all the information publicly available on the project reaching different audiences. Its content has, and will be, regularly updated to keep raising interest and awareness around the project topic and activities.

In this deliverable, one journal paper, 12 contributions to conferences and workshops have been reported plus one industrial article and several invited talks. It is expected that this publication activity will be increased in the second half of the project as more technical results, including experimental ones, become available. Therefore, submission of scientific papers in conferences and journals will be one of the primary goals for the next reporting period.

Progress in the project activities and recent events will be reported through regular newsletters. Social media channels will be employed more intensively to timely inform interested parties about important events or news about ULTRAWAVE.

After the successful experience of the shared booth at the European Microwave Week, the ICT Beyond 5G Cluster is intensifying its activity with high media impact. The leverage of the resources of the seven consortia permits a level of dissemination precluded to an isolated consortium.

In the next reporting period new joint actions will be reported.

ULTRAWAVE consortium is committed to continue with a regular and effective dissemination to reinforce the awareness of the project among specialists and general public, by using effectively social media and online tools, through participation in relevant conferences and workshops and publishing the project results in relevant journals and conferences.

Annex I NEWSLETTERS

The first newsletter, below, was made public on March 2018. It can be downloaded from the project website.

Welcome to ULTRAWAVE !

My vision of future wireless data distribution is of cities covered with a dense mantle of data to feed mobile networks, small cells, fixed access with unprecedented capacity and flexibility.

The H2020 ULTRAWAVE project aims to translate this vision in a beyond 5G physical layer enabled by state of the art devices, components and systems at millimetre wave above 100 GHz. I have the privilege to coordinate a consortium of outstanding scientists from eight institutions of 5 European countries, with the broadest range of expertise, including vacuum electronics, millimetre wave integrated circuits, photonics and advanced microfabrication, for creating the highest capacity layer that the technology can conceive so far, by exploiting in full the millimetre wave portion of the spectrum.

By combining area sectors in Point to multipoint at D-band (141 – 148.5) connected by high capacity links at G-band (275 – 300 GHz), ULTRAWAVE aims to produce ultracapacity layers with more than 100 Gb/s/km² of area capacity to satisfy the unstoppable growth of wireless data. The high transmission power of new generation traveling wave amplifiers will permit to contrast the high atmosphere attenuation, that has so far prevented to cover wide area with a single wide antenna beam.

The project has formidable challenges, the D-band and G-band technology are not yet mature and need advanced approaches to achieve the enabling system performance. This project will bring the Europe at the apex of the wireless millimetre wave technology worldwide.

The three years of the ULTRAWAVE project will be an exciting race in the millimetre wave spectrum technology with synergies from all the most advanced electronics technologies.

Claudio Paoloni
 ULTRAWAVE Coordinator

ULTRAWAVE Consortium

<p>This project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union</p>	<p>START: 1st September 2017 DURATION: 36 months REFERENCE: 762119</p>	<p>Project Coordinator: Prof. Claudio Paoloni c.paoloni@lancaster.ac.uk</p>
<p>www.ULTRAWAVE2020.eu</p>		

Consortium at a glance

ULTRAWAVE consortium is made of eight partners from EU five countries: United Kingdom, Germany, France, Italy and Spain.

It includes three SMEs: OMMIC (France), HFSE (Germany) and Fibernova (Spain); one research institute, Ferdinand-Braun-Institut (Germany); and four universities: University of Lancaster (UK), Goethe University of Frankfurt (Germany), University of Rome Tor Vergata (Italy) and Universitat Politècnica de València (Spain).

Project description

ULTRAWAVE addresses the need for new backhauling technologies able to provide ultra-capacity cell density for 5G and future generation networks, aiming at providing more than 100 Gbps/km². To enable a competitive backhaul for such high cell densification, ULTRAWAVE concept combines, for the first time, a Point-to-multiPoint (PtM) system in the D-band (141 – 148.5 GHz) fed by a Point-to-Point (PtP) system in the G-band (275 – 305 GHz).

ULTRAWAVE concept is allowed by the development of new traveling wave tubes in combination with solid-state electronics and photonics. This new layer will enable backhaul of hundreds of small and pico cells, no matter the density, opening scenarios for new network paradigms aiming at a full 5G implementation.

Objectives

- Exploitation of the whole millimeter wave spectrum both in Point-to-MultiPoint and Point-to-Point for the maximum flexibility in network architecture to respond to the irreversible traffic growth.
- Demonstration of two novel Travelling Wave Tubes at D-band and G-band and a full European chipset for D-band and G-band.
- First outdoor demonstration of a Point-to-MultiPoint system at the D-band and a Point-to-Point as true “fiber on air” at the G-band

The footer banner is dark blue with white text and logos. On the left is the European Union flag logo. Next to it, the text reads: "This project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union". In the center, the text reads: "START: 1st September 2017", "DURATION: 36 months", and "REFERENCE: 762119". On the right, the text reads: "Project Coordinator: Prof. Claudio Paoloni" and "c.paoloni@lancaster.ac.uk". Below the text are the LinkedIn and Twitter logos. At the bottom center, the website "www.ULTRAWAVE2020.eu" is displayed. On the bottom right, the number "3" is shown. The background of the banner is a city skyline at night.

ULTRAWAVE in the news

- The British magazine “The Engineer” published on September 2017 the article “UK team leads European effort to pioneer high speed wireless data coverage”
- The Spanish newspaper “La Vanguardia” published on September 2017 the article “Proyecto europeo de la UPV busca conexiones inalámbricas de alta eficiencia” in Spanish describing ULTRAWAVE project.
- A German press release was published in September 2017 to announce the start of the project in German

Project Meetings

ULTRAWAVE kick-off meeting was held on September 14th – 15th, 2017 at the Lancaster University, Lancaster, UK. It was organized in two sessions: a one day workshop open to public and one private meeting to kickoff the project.

The kickoff workshop was titled “Wireless communications toward the 300 GHz. It included invited speakers from When-AB (France), University of Surrey (UK) and Huawei (Italy) and talks from all the ULTRAWAVE partners. A panel session moderated by the Coordinator, Claudio Paoloni closed the workshop. The discussion highlighted that the millimetre-waves are the only solution for flexible 5G backhauling. The wide bandwidth available allows to handle the expected large increases in aggregated traffic; equipment and antenna small size, reduce substantially the OPEX if Point to multipoint is used.

The first six months General Assembly of ULTRAWAVE was held at the Ferdinand Braun Institute (FBH) in Berlin, Germany, on the 1st-2nd of February 2018. After the welcome by Viktor Krozer, the Consortium discussed for two days on the implementation the main workpackages and tasks

Panel discussion during the kick-off meeting workshop

Six Month Progress Meeting held at FBH facilities in Berlin, Germany.

ULTRAWAVE Dissemination

ULTRAWAVE partners presented the first results of the project in several conferences:

- “26th European Conference on Networks and Communications” ([EuCNC2017](#)), Oulu (Finland), 12th -15th June 2017. Claudio Paoloni presented the talk “Point to Multipoint at Millimetre Waves Above 90 GHz”.
- “European Microwave Week” ([EuMW2017](#)), Nuremberg, Germany), October 2017. Claudio. Paoloni gave a presentation on “Wireless Communications Towards the 300 GHz”.
- “IET Colloquium on Millimetre-wave and Terahertz Engineering & Technology 2018”, Birmingham, UK, 1st March 2018. Rupa Basu gave a talk on “Wireless Communications Towards the 300 GHz”.
- Workshop “Towards TeraHertz Communications Workshop”, organized by the European Commission Brussels, Belgium, 7th March 2018. ULTRAWAVE coordinator, C. Paoloni, chaired session 2, titled “Physical layer techniques for THz communication” at the workshop and described the key innovations of ULTRAWAVE through the presentation entitled “Ultracapacity layer enabled by novel traveling wave tubes”.

Claudio Paoloni presenting ULTRAWAVE

Forthcoming events

ULTRAWAVE will be present in the next upcoming conferences:

- “IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference” ([WCNC 2018](#)) to be held in Barcelona, Spain, from the 15th to the 18th April 2018.
ULTRAWAVE coordinator, C. Paoloni, is co-organizer of the Industry Panel “[Economics and Adoption of Millimeter Wave Technology in Future Networks](#)”.
- “IEEE International Vacuum Electronics Conference” ([IVEC 2018](#)), to be held in Monterey, USA, from the 24th to the 26th April 2018.
C. Paoloni, R. Letizia, V. Krozer, M. Marilier, S. Boppel, A. Ramirez, B. Vidal, E. Limiti, R. Zimmerman, “Toward 100 Gbps Wireless Networks Enabled by Millimeter Wave Traveling Wave Tubes”.
- “European Conference on Networks and Communications” ([EuCNC 2018](#)) to be held in Ljubljana, Slovenia, from the 18th to the 21st June 2018. A Special Session ““Terabit Wireless Transport for Networks Beyond 5G”, has been organised and it will be chaired by Claudio Paoloni.
- “20th International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks” ([ICTON 2018](#)), Bucharest (Romania), from the 1st to the 5th July 2018. B. Vidal will discuss the use of photonic technologies for mm-wave backhaul networks.
- “European Microwave Week” ([EuMW 2018](#)) to be held in Madrid, Spain, from the 23rd to the 28th September 2018. A booth will be shared among several projects of the call.

In the spotlight... Fibernova

We are going to focus in the last section of the newsletter on one of the industrial partners of ULTRAWAVE. In this first issue, we are going to discover more details about Fibernova Systems.

Fibernova Systems is a small company located in Valencia, Spain, that started in 2010 with a clear vocation towards setting new landmarks in the Telecommunications Industry both in Wireless and Optical communication fields.

With a strong scientific background provided by the Technical University of Valencia and its spin-off DAS Photonics, together with the support of its main shareholder Fibernet, a major Spanish photonic systems manufacturer, Fibernova is ideally positioned to reach its objectives of contributing to the Telecommunications ecosystem with engineering services and high-value products.

In its first years, Fibernova acquired first-hand experience of the state of the art of the Telecommunications networks with different turn-key deployments for Spanish operators. The company realized the importance of field-testing new technologies before deploying them to real application environments. Small-scale deployments, within controlled environments, together with well-defined testing protocols and training of the installation personnel can provide time and money savings to companies willing to introduce new technologies.

In its short trajectory since 2010, Fibernova has participated in four EU-funded research projects: FIVER and SARABAND in FP7, TWEETHER and ULTRAWAVE in H2020. Since SARABAND Project (2011), Fibernova has been part of European consortiums being responsible for the Field Trial activities for different wireless technologies. In H2020 ULTRAWAVE, the key is to demonstrate wireless communications at untapped frequency bands such as 120 GHz and 300 GHz. Fibernova will devise a field trial tailored in terms of range, capacity and number of nodes to be interconnected to the technology being developed in the consortium.

Deployment examples by Fibernova Systems

<p>This project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union</p>	<p>START: 1st September 2017 DURATION: 36 months REFERENCE: 762119</p>	<p>Project Coordinator: Prof. Claudio Paoloni c.paoloni@lancaster.ac.uk</p>
<p>www.ULTRAWAVE2020.eu</p>		<p></p> <p style="text-align: right;">6</p>

In the spotlight... Fibernova Systems

Interview with Antonio Ramirez, Project Manager at Fibernova, leader of ULTRAWAVE's WP6 "System testing and proof of concept in realistic scenarios".

• **How is working in a high-tech company like Fibernova?**

The participation of Fibernova in H2020 initiatives such as the ongoing TWEETHER and ULTRAWAVE projects provides us with a deep insight of the research and development process leading to new mm-wave components and systems that will allow wireless communications in frequency bands that could not be used with the current state of the art of the technology.

Antonio Ramirez from Fibernova Systems

Being ready for the Field Trial of both projects is an important responsibility for us, after witnessing all the efforts of our partners to overcome technological limitations and achieve the objectives of the program. Fibernova's main role is to contribute to the development process with an operational point of view and prepare a testing environment within UPV Campus to test the developed equipment and prove its performances. The latter implies that Fibernova is responsible of managing a campus-wide network linking several buildings where the different wireless nodes can be tested, registering the achieved performances during significant periods (weeks, months) and correlating the results with weather conditions such as rain intensity.

• **What are the usual challenges that you face in your company?**

The main challenges for Fibernova are ensuring the Field Trial runs smoothly, minimizing unexpected incidences that could interrupt the performance assessment of the systems under test. In order to achieve that, every system in the network needs to be monitored and key parameter indicators analysed to detect and possibly avoid downtimes of the testing network. We have as well the need of continuously upgrading the network performances to be able to test high speed networks such as ULTRAWAVE's.

• **What do you think is the most interesting fact about ULTRAWAVE project?**

The ULTRAWAVE Project shall open the frontier of new frequency bands above 100GHz to the Telecommunications industry. From the beginning of the project, the efforts of the scientific and industrial partners to push the barriers of the technology are being outstanding. Being able to test in 2020, together with UPV, the first prototypes of 120 GHz and 300 GHz communications systems to be developed in ULTRAWAVE is an enticing perspective and a great motivation for the company to provide the consortium with valuable contributions towards a successful demonstration.

The second newsletter, see below, was made public on January 2019. It can also be downloaded from the project website.

Foreword

The European Commission Horizon 2020 ULTRAWAVE has completed its first year of activity. On the 8th November 2018 the first annual review meeting has assessed the results of the project:

The second ULTRAWAVE newsletter includes:

- updates on the technological progress of the project,
- a summary of the key events where ULTRAWAVE participated,
 - Conferences
 - Workshop organization
 - ICT Beyond 5G Cluster
- the forthcoming events
 - Second Toward Terahertz Communication Workshop
- Meet the ULTRAWAVE partners
 - the Ferdinand Braun Institute (Germany).

Stay tuned, please visit our webpage www.ultrawave2020.eu and twitter [@ultrawave2020](https://twitter.com/ultrawave2020)

ULTRAWAVE video is online!

A short promotional video to simply describe the aim of ULTRAWAVE is online in the ULTRAWAVE Channel of YouTube.

[Click to watch it](#)

Project Coordinator:
Professor Claudio Paoloni
c.paoloni@lancaster.ac.uk

Start: 1st September 2017
Duration: 36 months
Reference: 762119

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 762119

www.ultrawave2020.eu

Technology

The specifications of ULTRAWAVE systems and its components and the deployment scenario have been defined and summarized in the public Deliverable D2.1.

It includes also the system specifications of the Transmission Hub and Terminal for the D-band Point to multi point, as well as for the G-band Point to Point links. In particular it describes the the specifications of the D-band and G-band TWTs, the MMIC chipsets at D-band and G-band and the G-band photonic transmitter.

The link specifications are summarized in the table below, 99.99% availability is assumed in ITU zone K

FUNCTION	Architecture	Frequency	Capacity	Range
Fronthaul	PtP	G-band	~* 30 Gbps	600-700 m
Backhaul	PmP	D-band	~* 30 Gbps	600 m

- The design and simulation of the D-band Traveling Wave Tube (TWT) is concluded. The TWT uses the double corrugated waveguide as slow wave structure. The first fabrication test of the double corrugated waveguide has been successful. The fabrication of the electron gun, collector and full slow wave structure are in progress.

Microphotograph of the fabricated D-Band high power amplifier

TWT rendering

- The design and fabrication of the D-band Low Noise Amplifier and the mixers are in progress
- The design of the G-band power amplifier and frequency converter design has started.
- The design for the photonic transmitter has been finalized.

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Project Meetings

A virtual General Assembly was held in July 2018 by Webex

A second General Assembly was held in Madrid, Spain, on the 26th of September 2018. It was scheduled during European Microwave Week (EuMW) 2018, where ULTRAWAVE participated with the booth at the exhibition.

The General Assembly was preparatory to the first review meeting on the 8th November.

All the activities of the active workpackages were discussed and the planning for the second year of the project finalized.

View of the General Assembly

ULTRAWAVE - ICT Beyond 5G Cluster

ULTRAWAVE is member of the ICT Beyond 5G Cluster founded by the projects of the call ICT-09-2017 "Networking research beyond 5G" of EU H2020 program, to collaborate in the dissemination of their results. The cluster includes six H2020 projects, TERAPOD, DREAM, EPIC, TERRANOVA, WORTECS and ULTRAWAVE, funded by the ITC-09-2017 Call and one project, THOR, funded by the joint EU-Japan call. The main last activities of the ICT Beyond 5G cluster have been:

- A booth at the European Microwave Week 2018 (EuMW), held in Madrid (Spain) from the 25th September to 27th September 2018, was jointly organized by the ICT Beyond 5G cluster projects. Posters outlining the key aspects of the projects were displayed. In addition, leaflets and components were also shown. ULTRAWAVE showed a 3D model built at Lancaster University by additive manufacturing of the new D-band TWT.
- The second "Toward THz Communications Workshop", is being organized by the ICT-09-2017 Cluster (more information on the next page).

Prof. Claudio Paoloni, ULTRAWAVE coordinator, showing a 3D model of the TWT to Prof. Edward Wasige, University of Glasgow.

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Second Toward THz Communications Workshop

The Second “Toward THz Communications Workshop” will be held at Albert Borschette Congress Centre (CCAB), Brussels (Belgium) on Thursday 7th March 2019.

The international event is organized by the ICT Beyond 5G cluster.

Professor Claudio Paoloni is the General Chair, together with Dr. Alan Davy.

The workshop will be an opportunity to bring together key actors in THz communications and discuss the future perspectives of the field.

The workshop is supported by the European Commission and the IEEE Future Networks.

The announcement can be downloaded at

[Programme](#)

Registration free of charge at

[Register here](#)

Plenary Session: Toward THz Communications

Plenary Chair Claudio Paoloni, Lancaster University, UK

Introduction to the ICT-09-2017 Cluster

Dr. Alan Davy; Waterford Institute of Technology, Ireland

*EC perspective on the challenges of THz communications
European Commission*

*European flagship on THz science and technology-TERAFLAG
Dr.-Ing Yaning Zou; TU Dresden, Germany*

*Recent Japanese developments on THz communications
Prof. Tadao Nagatsuma; Osaka University, Japan*

*Terahertz wireless communications: a photonics perspective
Prof. Daniel Mittleman; Brown University, USA*

Session 1: THz Communication Electronic and Photonic Components and Systems

Session Chair Angeliki Alexiou, University of Piraeus, Greece

Photonic approaches to THz communications

Prof. Guillaume Ducournau; University of Lille, France

*ULTRAWAVE – Technology for D-band Point to multi-point distribution
Prof. Claudio Paoloni; University of Lancaster, UK*

DREAM – D-band Radio solution Enabling up to 100 Gbps reconfigurable Approach for Meshed beyond 5G networks

Dr. Vladimir Ermolov; VTT, Finland

*TERAPOD – Terahertz-based ultra-high bandwidth wireless access networks
Prof. Cyril Renaud; University College London, UK*

*THz micromachining – enabling the large-scale exploitation of the THz frequency spectrum?
Prof. Joachim Oberhammer; KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden*

Session 2: THz Communication Networks, Protocols and Architectures and User Cases

Session Chair Thomas Kürner, TU Braunschweig, Germany

Opening the THz-spectrum for communication for 5G and beyond

Dr. Wolfgang Tempel; Nokia Bell Labs, Germany

*EPIC – Enabling Practical Wireless Tb/s Communications with Next Generation Channel Coding
Dr. Onur Sahin; InterDigital, UK*

TERRANOVA – Terabit/s Wireless Connectivity by TeraHertz innovative technologies to deliver Optical Network Quality of Experience in Systems beyond 5G

Prof. Angeliki Alexiou; University of Piraeus, Greece

*THz Communication Networks, Protocols and Architectures and User Cases
Dr. Yinggang Li; Ericsson, Sweden*

Session 3: THz Communication Spectrum and Physical Layer

Session Chair Onur Sahin, InterDigital, UK

Standards aspects of THz communications

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Thomas Kürner; TU Braunschweig, Germany

*WORTECS – Wireless Optical/Radio Tera-bit CommunicationS
Mr. Olivier Bouchet; Orange, France*

*End user perspective on THz communication spectrum and physical layer
Dr. Petr Jurčík; Deutsche Telekom, Czech Republic*

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ULTRAWAVE publications, talks and events.

- The ULTRAWAVE coordinator, Prof. Claudio Paoloni gave a plenary talk to discuss the application of TWTs for millimeter wave wireless networks, titled “Novel High Capacity Millimetre Wave Wireless Networks Enabled by Traveling Wave Tubes” at the CST European User Conference (EUC), Unterschleissheim, Germany, 4th June 2018.
- Prof. Claudio Paoloni, chaired the Special Session “Terabit wireless transport for networks beyond 5G”, European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC 2018), Ljubljana (Slovenia), 18-21 June 2018
- C. Paoloni, “Ultra Capacity Wireless Layer Beyond 100 GHz Based on Millimeter Wave Traveling Wave Tubes”, European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC), Ljubljana (Slovenia), 18-21 June 2018.
- B. Vidal, “Photonic-assisted G-band wireless links for 5G backhaul”, 20th International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON), Bucharest (Romania), 1-5 July 2018.
- G. Ulisse, V. Krozer, “Folded waveguide traveling wave tube in a parallel configuration with a single electron beam”, IEEE International Vacuum Electronics Conference (IVEC), Monterey (USA), 24-26 April 2018.
- C. Paoloni, R. Letizia, V. Krozer, M. Marilier, S. Boppel, A. Ramirez, B. Vidal, E. Limiti, R. Zimmerman, “Toward 100 Gbps Wireless Networks Enabled by Millimeter Wave Traveling Wave Tubes”, IEEE International Vacuum Electronics Conference (IVEC), Monterey (USA) 24-26 April 2018.

Claudio Paoloni at EuCNC 2018

ULTRAWAVE will participate at:

- ULTRAWAVE will participate in the next upcoming events:
- “Second Towards THz Communications Workshop”, organized by the ICT Beyond 5G Cluster in Brussels, Belgium, 7th March 2019.
 - “European Conference on Networks and Communications” (EuCNC 2019), Valencia, Spain, 18 - 21 June 2019.
 - “44th International Conference on Infrared, Millimeter, and Terahertz Waves” (IRMMW-THz 2019) Paris, France, 1 – 6 September 2019.
 - “IEEE Second 5G World Forum” (WF-5G) Dresden, Germany, 30 September – 2 October 2019.

Project Coordinator:
 Professor Claudio Paoloni
 c.paoloni@lancaster.ac.uk

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Meet the ULTRAWAVE PARTNERS... Ferdinand Braun Institute

In our effort to present the partners and the people behind the research carried out in ULTRAWAVE, this second newsletter presents the Ferdinand-Braun-Institut (FBH) in Berlin (Germany).

The Ferdinand-Braun-Institut (FBH), the Leibniz-Institut für Höchstfrequenztechnik, is a research institute focused on electronic and optical components, modules and systems based on compound semiconductors. These devices are key enablers that address the needs of today's society in fields like communications, energy, health, and mobility.

Specifically, FBH develops light sources from the visible to the ultra-violet spectral range: high-power diode lasers with excellent beam quality, UV light sources and hybrid laser modules. Applications range from medical technology, high-precision metrology and sensors to optical communications in space.

In the field of microwaves, FBH develops high-efficiency multi-functional power amplifiers and millimeter wave frontends targeting energy-efficient mobile communications, industrial sensing and imaging as well as car safety systems. In addition, compact atmospheric microwave plasma sources operating with economic low-voltage drivers and laser drivers are fabricated for use in a variety of applications

The Ferdinand-Braun-Institut, Leibniz-Institut für Höchstfrequenztechnik

The FBH is a competence center for III-V compound semiconductors and has a strong international reputation. FBH competence covers the full range of capabilities, from design through fabrication to device characterization.

In close cooperation with industry, its research results lead to cutting-edge products. The institute also successfully turns innovative product ideas into spin-off companies. Overall, working in strategic partnerships with industry, FBH ensures German technological excellence in microwave and optoelectronic research.

Project Coordinator: Professor Claudio Paoloni c.paoloni@lancaster.ac.uk	Start: 1 st September 2017 Duration: 36 months Reference: 762119	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 762119	
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Meet the ULTRAWAVE partners: FBH

Interview with Dr. Sebastian Boppel, head of InP Devices Lab at FBH, providing InP MMIC technology to the project.

• How is working in a high-tech institute like your institute?

In my research career I have always been fascinated by pushing the frontiers of high speed electronics. At FBH, I have the opportunity to develop InP MMIC technology for relatively large output powers at high frequencies. The institute offers the value chain in-house, from device modeling, circuit design, MMIC fabrication and high frequency device characterization to mounting and assembly.

The MMIC process itself is a complex chain of processing steps; its development and execution require the collaboration of skilled scientists and technicians, a large variety of processing equipment as well as a standardized organization of processes. At the end of this long process chain, it is therefore always a pleasure to see the circuits being characterized and to supply the functional circuits within projects or to costumers.

Fully processed 3" wafer with monolithic integrated circuits based on InP DHBTs

Monolithic integrated circuits based on FBH's InP DHBT technology

• What are the usual challenges that you face in your institute?

For InP MMIC technology, you face two major challenges. The first is to provide sufficient transistor count in one circuit, which is basically a question of yield. We are able to fabricate circuits with 30 transistors with sufficient yield and are currently pushing for higher transistor counts. The second challenge is to advance the transistors in the direction of higher frequencies and higher output powers. Currently, we provide circuits up to 300 GHz and are about to enter the terahertz range..

• What do you think is the most interesting fact about ULTRAWAVE project?

The ULTRAWAVE project is an ideal match with our technology, since it requires components with relatively high output power and high linearity in the range from 100 GHz to 300 GHz. It is exciting to be part of a project which aims to open this frequency band for telecommunication providing high capacity backhaul over the air.

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Annex II PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

The first brochure of ULTRAWAVE, below, which can be downloaded from the project website.

ULTRAWAVE
ULTRA CAPACITY WIRELESS LAYER BEYOND 100 GHz BASED ON MILLIMETER WAVE TRAVELLING WAVE TUBES

ULTRAWAVE is aimed at developing a high capacity backhaul that enables 5G cell densification by exploiting bands beyond 100 GHz. New travelling wave tubes delivering high power will allow the creation of an ultra capacity layer providing more than 100 Gbps per kilometer square in Point-to-MultiPoint at D-band (141 – 174.8 GHz) fed by novel G-band (300 GHz) Point-to-Point high capacity links.

The ULTRAWAVE system is empowered by the development of new traveling wave tubes in combination with solid-state electronics and photonics. This new layer will enable backhaul of hundreds of small and pico cells, no matter the density, opening scenarios for new network paradigms aiming at a full 5G implementation.

ULTRAWAVE objectives:

- 1** Exploitation of the whole millimeter wave spectrum both in Point-to-MultiPoint and Point-to-Point for the maximum flexibility in network architecture to respond to the irreversible traffic growth.
- 2** Demonstration of two novel Travelling Wave Tubes at D-band and G-band and a full European chipset for D-band and G-band.
- 3** First outdoor demonstration of a Point-to-MultiPoint system at the D-band and a Point-to-Point as true "fiber on air" at the G-band

ULTRAWAVE TWT-enabled mm-wave Point-to-Multipoint concept

Horizon 2020 European Union

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START: 1st September 2017
DURATION: 36 months
REFERENCE: 762119

www.ultrawave2020.com

Logos: Lancaster University, fibernova, FBH Leibniz Ferdinand Brauns Institut, GOETHE UNIVERSITÄT FRANKFURT AM MAIN, HUBNER HF Systems Engineering, OMMIC Innovating with 5G, UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE VALÈNCIA, Università di Roma Tor Vergata

in

The second brochure of ULTRAWAVE, below, which can be downloaded from the project website.

ULTRAWAVE CONCEPT

ULTRAWAVE aims to the first ultracapacity layers with hundreds of Gigabit per second per kilometer square as solution for the unstoppable growth of wireless data.

ULTRAWAVE scenario envisages a high cell density backhaul network enabled by wireless Point-to-MultiPoint (PtmP) sectors at the D-band (141 – 148.5 GHz), fed by a fronthaul "fiber on air" based on Point-to-Point (PtP) links in the G-band (275 – 305 GHz) to cover wide city areas.

Novel travelling wave tubes are the enabling devices to provide transmission power at Watt level for links longer than 500 m.

NEW ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES

ULTRAWAVE concept brings a step change in millimeter wave technology. New traveling wave tubes, GaAs and InP monolithic microwave integrated circuits (MMICs) and photonic transmitter are the key components of the wireless revolution of ULTRAWAVE.

TWT

Traveling wave tubes are high power amplifiers based on the transfer of energy from a high energy electron beam to the radiofrequency signal.

One novel TWT will be designed and realized at the D-band and one at G-band with unprecedented performance at millimetre waves, with about 12 W and 2 W output power, respectively.

Formidable technology challenges have to be overcome due to the small dimensions of the parts that require advanced micromechanical processes.

High precision computer numerical control (CNC) milling will be combined with lithographic processes for affordable fabrication, enabling the exploitation of the potential market of millimetre-wave wireless networks.

MMICs

The first European chipset of monolithic microwave integrated circuits (MMICs) at D-band will be designed and fabricated using the 40 nm GaAs process for the Low Noise amplifiers (LNA), UP-converters, DOWN-converter and by 0.8 μm InP DHBT process for a power amplifier with 15 dBm output power.

The fabrication of the G-band MMICs is particularly challenging. A G-band LNA will be realized using 40 nm GaAs process in coplanar waveguide. The upconverter and the power amplifier, with 10 dBm output power, will be realized by the InP DHBT process.

Photonic Transmitter

A 48 Gbps photonic transmitter will be realized for exploiting G-band transmitters to combine the key advantages of photonics, ultrawide bandwidth, easy scalability in multi-channel transmission, antenna remoting and flexibility, with the long range provided by travelling wave tubes.

ULTRAWAVE addresses the need for new backhauling technologies able to provide ultra-capacity cell density for 5G and future generation networks, above the 100 Gbps/km² threshold.

The novelty of ULTRAWAVE is to design, fabricate and test a full set of components and systems to exploit the full millimetre wave spectrum up to 300 GHz by an ultra-capacity layer for wireless backhaul. New traveling wave tube amplifiers in combination with solid-state electronics and photonics will be the core of the ULTRAWAVE architecture. The ultra-capacity layer will enable backhaul of hundreds of small and pico cells, no matter the density, opening scenarios for new network paradigms aiming at a full 5G implementation.

ULTRAWAVE OBJECTIVES

- 1 Exploitation of the whole millimetre-wave spectrum both in Point-to-MultiPoint and Point-to-Point for the maximum flexibility in network architecture to respond to the irreversible traffic growth.
- 2 Realization of two novel Traveling Wave Tubes at D-band and G-band and a full European chipset at D-band and G-band.
- 3 First outdoor field test of a Point-to-MultiPoint system at D-band and a Point-to-Point as true "fibre on air" at the G-band.

ULTRAWAVE
ULTRA CAPACITY WIRELESS LAYER BEYOND 100 GHz BASED ON MILLIMETER WAVE TRAVELLING WAVE TUBES

ULTRAWAVE is a European Commission H2020 programme funded under "ICT-09-2017 - Networking research beyond 5G", aiming to a breakthrough in millimetre waves high capacity wireless backhaul for future mobile networks.

Project Coordinator: Prof. Claudio Paoloni
Lancaster University, Lancaster, UK
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Consortium

- Lancaster University
- GOETHE UNIVERSITÄT FRANKFURT AM MAIN
- HUBNER HF System Engineering
- Università di Roma Tor Vergata
- COMMIC innovating with III-V's
- fibernova
- FBH Leibniz Ferdinand Braun Institut
- UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE VALÈNCIA

This project has received funding, 2.9 M€, from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 762119. It started on September 1st, 2017 and will end on August 31th, 2020.

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